

Supplementary material to the article “Building legitimacy: Audience trust as a pillar of public service media”

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Annex A: Descriptive Statistics for Predictors

Descriptive analysis of the distribution of responses to the question “In your opinion, how important, or not, are publicly funded news services such as RTP to society?” across the three dimensions under analysis (sociodemographics; news use; and attitudes towards news).

Table A.1. Crosstabulation of Perception on the Importance of Public Service Media to society with Sociodemographic Factors

		Unimportant / Indifferent			Important		
Sociodemographics		n	%	Mean	n	%	Mean
Gender	Male	299	32,3%	---	627	67,7%	---
	Female	319	31,2%	---	702	68,8%	---
Age		618	---	46,8	1329	---	48,1
Education	Primary (ISCED 1 and 2)	305	37,8%	---	501	62,2%	---
	Secondary (ISCED 3 and 4)	176	29,9%	---	413	70,1%	---
	Tertiary (ISCED 5 to 8)	137	24,8%	---	415	75,2%	---
Political orientation	Undeclared / not positioned	182	44,7%	---	225	55,3%	---
	Left	174	23,8%	---	558	76,2%	---

Center	98	28,7%	---	243	71,3%	---
Right	164	35,1%	---	303	64,9%	---

Source: own elaboration from Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2023 data

Observing Table A.1, there are no substantial differences between genders regarding the evaluation of the importance of public service media (PSM) for society, with nearly identical proportions of men (67,7%) and women (68,8%) considering it important. Regarding age, the group that views PSM as important differs only slightly in average age compared to those who view it as unimportant or indifferent (48,1 years versus 46,8 years, a difference of 1,3 years).

In terms of education and household income, there is a clear trend: individuals with higher levels of education and higher income tend to perceive PSM as more important to society. For example, 75,2% of respondents with tertiary education view PSM as important, compared to 70,1% with secondary education and 62,2% with primary education. Similarly, 75,6% of individuals in the high-income group consider PSM important, compared to 68,3% in the medium-income group and 63,9% in the low-income group.

Political orientation also reveals notable differences. Respondents on the left are the most likely to view PSM as important (76,2%), followed by those in the center (71,3%) and those on the right (64,9%). In contrast, the undecided or undeclared group stands out, with only 55,3% perceiving PSM as important to society, a marked difference compared to all three declared political orientations.

Table A.2. Crosstabulation of Perception on the Importance of Public Service Media to society with News Usage Factors

News Use		Unimportant / Indifferent			Important		
		n	%	Mean	n	%	Mean
Frequency of news consumption		618	---	2,9	1329	---	3,0
Used RTP (e.g. RTP1, 2) TV channels last week	No	523	36,5%	---	908	63,5%	---
	Yes	95	18,4%	---	421	81,6%	---
Used RDP Antena 1 radio last week	No	580	32,1%	---	1225	67,9%	---
	Yes	38	26,8%	---	104	73,2%	---
Used RTP 3 TV channel last week	No	542	33,8%	---	1060	66,2%	---
	Yes	76	22,0%	---	269	78,0%	---

Source: own elaboration from Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2023 data

Considering Table A.2, which presents variables related to news usage, the evaluation of PSM is relatively consistent regardless of the frequency of news consumption. However, notable differences emerge when comparing users and non-users of RTP's media brands. Among those who used RTP1 and RTP2 generalist TV channels in the last week, 81,6% consider PSM to be important to society, compared to only 63,5% of non-users. Similarly, 73,2% of respondents who listened to Antena 1 public radio in the last week view PSM as important, compared to 67,9% of those who did not. Finally, 78% of those who watched RTP3, the dedicated news channel, consider PSM important, in contrast to 66,2% of non-viewers.

Table A.3. Crosstabulation of Perception on the Importance of Public Service Media to society with Attitudes Towards News Factors

		Unimportant / Indifferent			Important		
Attitudes towards news		n	%	Mean	n	%	Mean
Trust most news most of the time	Tends to distrust	392	49,0%	---	408	51,0%	---
	Tends to trust	226	19,7%	---	921	80,3%	---
Trusts RTP Brand		618	---	7,1	1329	---	9,0
Concern about what is real and fake online	Tends to be unconcerned	256	48,3%	---	274	51,7%	---
	Tends to be concerned	362	25,5%	---	1055	74,5%	---
Stories selected for me by editors and journalists is good	Tends to disagree	470	39,6%	---	716	60,4%	---
	Tends to agree	148	19,4%	---	613	80,6%	---

Source: own elaboration from Reuters Institute Digital News Report 2023 data

Finally, regarding Table A.3, attitudes towards news appear to be associated with a more positive perception of public service media (PSM). Respondents who tend to trust most news most of the time are significantly more likely to view PSM as important to society (80,3%) compared to those who tend to distrust news (51%). Similarly, trust in the RTP brand is linked to a higher average perception of PSM's importance (mean score of 9 versus 7,1 among those who do not trust RTP).

Concern about online disinformation also correlates with perceptions of PSM's importance, with 74,5% of those who are concerned about real versus fake information online rating PSM as important, compared to 51,7% of those who are unconcerned. Furthermore, individuals who agree that stories selected by professional editors and

journalists are good tend to consider PSM more important (80,6%) than those who disagree (60,4%).

Annex B: Logistic Regression Supplementary Results

Table B.1. Model 1 – Sociodemographics

	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	OR / Exp(B)
Female (vs male)	0,05	0,102	0,245	0,621	1,052
Age	0,002	0,004	0,381	0,537	1,002
Secondary education (vs primary)	0,274	0,12	5,173	0,023	1,315
Tertiary education (vs primary)	0,432	0,129	11,221	<0,001	1,540
Political left (vs undeclared)	0,755	0,141	28,807	<0,001	2,128
Political center (vs undeclared)	0,488	0,163	8,947	0,003	1,629
Political right (vs undeclared)	0,237	0,148	2,554	0,110	1,267
Constant	0,051	0,197	0,067	0,796	1,052

Table B.2. Model 2 – News Usage

	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	OR / Exp(B)
Female (vs male)	0,148	0,106	1,966	0,161	1,16
Age	-0,001	0,004	0,166	0,684	0,999
Secondary education (vs primary)	0,21	0,122	2,955	0,086	1,234
Tertiary education (vs primary)	0,333	0,132	6,386	0,012	1,395
Political left (vs undeclared)	0,642	0,143	20,033	<0,001	1,9
Political center (vs undeclared)	0,427	0,166	6,632	0,01	1,532
Political right (vs undeclared)	0,185	0,151	1,517	0,218	1,204
Frequency of news consumption	0,051	0,044	1,333	0,248	1,052
Used RTP last week	0,76	0,137	30,571	<0,001	2,138
Used Antena 1 last week	-0,155	0,211	0,539	0,463	0,856
Used RTP 3 last week	0,24	0,156	2,347	0,125	1,271
Constant	-0,067	0,23	0,085	0,77	0,935

Table B.3. Model 3 – Attitudes towards news

	B	S.E.	Wald	Sig.	OR / Exp(B)
Female (vs male)	0,047	0,118	0,157	0,692	1,048
Age	-0,007	0,004	2,596	0,107	0,993
Secondary education (vs primary)	0,16	0,136	1,37	0,242	1,173
Tertiary education (vs primary)	0,22	0,147	2,241	0,134	1,246
Political left (vs undeclared)	0,283	0,16	3,116	0,078	1,327
Political center (vs undeclared)	0,131	0,185	0,505	0,477	1,14
Political right (vs undeclared)	-0,096	0,169	0,323	0,570	0,908
Frequency of news consumption	-0,069	0,049	1,978	0,160	0,933
Used RTP last week	0,697	0,15	21,465	<0,001	2,007
Used Antena 1 last week	-0,019	0,235	0,007	0,934	0,981
Used RTP 3 last week	0,112	0,171	0,428	0,513	1,119
Trust in news	0,591	0,122	23,505	<0,001	1,806
Trust in RTP	0,348	0,031	125,686	<0,001	1,416
Concern about disinformation	0,544	0,125	18,943	<0,001	1,723
News curation by journalists is good	0,53	0,125	17,886	<0,001	1,700
Constant	-2,82	0,332	71,984	<0,001	0,06